

Geological Analysis and Spatial Distribution of the European Lithium Deposits

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Abstract

The present paper aims to highlight the major occurrences of lithium (Li) deposits, namely brine and hard-rock deposits. Based on their origin, there are two types of Li hard rock deposits in Europe, magmatic and sedimentary. Overall, 35 Li deposits have been identified, which may partially cover Europe's future demand for Li-based compounds.

European Lithium Deposits – Exploitation Potential

The European Union (EU) supports emphatically the green transition through its main strategic plans, namely the European Green Deal and the Horizon Europe key funding programme for research and innovation [1]. Electric Vehicles (EVs), which are the primary tool to decarbonize the transportation sector, depend on Li-ion batteries (LIBs). Therefore, the exploitation of Li deposits in Europe is vital towards reducing its dependence on imports. The projection of Li demand for 2030 is estimated at 3.7 million tons lithium carbonate equivalent (LCE) [2]. Lithium is predominantly concentrated in two deposit types, the “brine” deposits, characterized by a Li content not exceeding 0.1% Li₂O and “hard-rock” deposits with a Li content up to 1.0% Li₂O [3, 4].

The lacustrine evaporites, which constitute significant Li occurrences, are mainly located within tectonically active basins, delimited by active fault zones, and they are spotted in the upper parts of the geological time scale; these formations are associated with the brine deposits. Regarding the formation processes, water (e.g. groundwater, spring water, etc.) evaporates at high rate under arid to hyper-arid conditions, resulting in thin- to thick-bedded occurrences of evaporites ([5] and references therein). It is worth mentioning that brine deposits are linked to a unique Li source. Nevertheless, the most common scenario considers a magmatic heat source that causes weathering of felsic formations [6] and potential hydrothermal activity. The brine deposits are mainly located in North and South America and particularly in the USA, Argentina, Chile and Bolivia [7], while significant deposits are also present in some tectonically active basins (e.g. Qaidam) of China ([8] and references therein).

Moreover, the magmatic and weathering processes result in the formation of hard-rock deposits in magmatic and sedimentary rocks. In particular, these rock types contain minerals such as pyroxenes, phosphates, micas and silicates with significant Li content. Among them, jadarite is associated with one of the most significant deposits globally, located in Serbia [9].

Concerning Europe, hard-rock Li deposits, both magmatic and sedimentary, have been found [10]. According to Gourcerol [11], the following distinct categories of magmatic Li deposits exist in Europe: i) Rare-metal granites (RMG), ii) Lithium-Cesium-Tantalum (LCT) pegmatites, iii) Greisen, iv) Quartz-montebrazite hydrothermal veins and v) Tosudite mineralization related to gold deposits, while the sedimentary ones include: i) Jadar deposit type, ii) Mn-(Fe) deposits and iii) Bauxite deposits. Considering the above categories, the major Li deposits exist in (Figure 1): 1) Austria (Wolfsberg), 2) Czech Republic (Cinovec), 3) England (Meldon aplite quarry, St Austel), 4) Finland (Emmes, Hirvikallio, Kietymäki, Länttä, Leviäkangas, Outovesi, Rapasaari, Syväjärvi), 5) France (Beauvoir, Chédeville, Montebraz, Tréguennec - Prat-ar-Hastel, Tréguennec – Tréluan), 6) Germany (Altenberg, Cornelia Mine, Sadisdorf, Silbergrube, Zinnwald), 7) Ireland: (Aclare), 8) Portugal (Alijo, Alvarrões, Argemela, Mina do Barroso, Romano/Sepeda), 9) Serbia: (Jadar), 10) Spain (Alberta II, Valdeflórez/San José), 11) Ukraine (Nadiya, Polokhovskoe, Shevchenkovskoe, Stankovaskoe).

Figure 1. Distribution of lithium deposits in European countries (Austria, Czech Republic, England, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Portugal, Serbia, Spain and Ukraine); the number of Li deposits in each country is also shown).

The last years intensive research efforts are carried out, mainly in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme, to develop cost efficient technologies with reduced carbon footprint for the exploitation, processing and extraction of Critical Raw Materials (CRM) including energy transition metals such as Li. In this frame, EXCEED project entitled “Cost-effective, sustainable and responsible extraction routes for recovering distinct critical metals and industrial minerals as by-products from key European hard-rock lithium projects”, <https://exceed-horizon.eu/>, aims to unleash the full CRM and industrial mineral potential of Europe’s vast Li LCT-pegmatite and Rare-Metal Granite hard-rock resources (Figure 2). In addition, EXCEED aims to carry out a novel, integrated Life-Cycle, Techno-Economic and Human Impact Assessment, which will incorporate Social License to Operate (SLO) principles for the newly developed, mineral-centric, integrated processing routes for LCT-pegmatites and RMGs [12].

Figure 2. EXCEED’s Horizon Europe Pert Chart

It is known that present Li extraction process can be successfully applied for the treatment of high-grade Li ores however, they are not considered adequate for the treatment of low-grade resources [13].

Furthermore, with the increasing pressure of environmental protection, new improved and with lower environmental footprint Li extraction technologies from ores containing minerals such as spodumene, lepidolite, petalite and mica need to be developed [14].

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Conclusions

With transport responsible for more than a quarter of the world's CO₂ emissions, the number of electric vehicles powered by lithium batteries, is anticipated to increase dramatically in the following years. As a result, the continuously increasing Li demand in Europe, related to the green transition, requires its exploitation from all available deposits. Geologically, the European lithium deposits belong to the hard-rock type and are located in several countries. Furthermore, new advanced technologies are required for the exploitation of Li ores and the production of battery-grade Li compounds (e.g., LiOH·H₂O, Li₂CO₃).

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